

Evaluation of Initial Damage and Stress Corrosion of GFRP

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ABSTRACT

On tensile testing under acidic environment, drastic strength reduction occurred as a result of acid attack, with crack-development under the load. The increase of micro-fracture with increasing immersion time was confirmed even at a fairly low load by measuring AE activity, because of the existence of the damage allowing acid to penetrate through GFRP. AE activity of tensile tests in acidic condition was strongly influenced by the toughness of matrix resin due to the crack resistance.

Keywords: GFRP, Initial damage, Acidic environment, Acoustic emission, Stress corrosion

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, composite materials have been widely used in many fields, due to their anti-corrosion properties, especially in area of chemical equipment involving acids. For proper usage, it is very important to understand the behavior of GFRP under acid environments. An acid corrosion phenomenon, called environmental stress cracking, is well known in E-glass fibers, one of the constituents of GFRP [1,2]. Acid diffusion into a matrix resin, however, does not occur under zero load, as reported [3].

The formation of a specific plain failure surface on stress cracking under acidic conditions is caused by fiber breaking occurring at a lower stress than the bonding strength between the fiber and the resin. This implies that GFRP can be easily fractured at a fairly low stress, as compared with its original strength, by developing cracks to allow the rapid transport of acid in the resin, as reported by Hogg and Hull [1].

The chemical resistance of GFRP is generally evaluated by the retention of strength in the immersion test (ASTM C 581), under the condition of which the penetration of acid will be restricted. This often leads to misunderstanding in the evaluation of the results. With the test condition such as immersion of pre-stressed specimen, on the contrary, useful data can be obtained. This is because the damage, locally developed in the GFRP even at a low stress, enables acid to penetrate through the resin. This results in acid attacking the fibers and influencing the bond strength in fiber/resin interface.

In detecting the damage, AE technique has successfully been used, for the stress failure of unidirectional GFRP and mat GFRP under acidic environment [4,5,6].

The present paper describes the recognition of initial damage developed under pre-stress by microscopic observation and the relationship between the generation of AE and the initial damage in tensile tests under air and acidic environments using test specimens with and without pre-stress. The SEM observation of the fracture surface of these specimens is also performed. It is confirmed that the existence of initial damage such as cracks governs the acid corrosion behavior of GFRP, in considering the test results with matrix resins having different toughness.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material and test specimen

The matrices were brittle bisphenol type unsaturated polyester resin (Resin A) and tough vinylester resin (Resin B) as shown in Table 1, and a plain woven cloth (Mie Textile YEM-2103) of E-glass fibers for reinforcement. A sheet was molded at room temperature by hand-lay-up method, using a spacer so as to maintain a constant thickness. It was post cured at 100C for 3 hrs., and dumbbell shaped specimens were machined out. The fiber volume fraction (V_f) was 37%. Thus, any form of anti-corrosive layers such as gel coating was not formed on the surface of the specimens.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of matrix resins.

Resin name	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Ultimate Strain (%)	Fracture Toughness (MNm ^{-3/2})
A	3.27	61.34	2.37	0.465
B	3.37	72.72	3.76	0.670

2.2 Conditions of pre-damaging and immersion

The specimens were pre-stressed to some extent, followed by immersion in 5% HNO₃ at room temperature. Tensile tests were conducted under air and acidic environments. The levels of stress for pre-damaging were 0, 30, 40, and 50% of the original tensile strength. Immersion time selected was 0, 1, 48, 148 and 720 hrs.

2.3 Tensile test and AE measurement

For the tensile test under the acidic environment, each specimen was mounted on an Instron 4206 testing machine fitted with plastic tube containing the acid solution, as shown in Fig.1. In addition to this, a PZT resonant transducer was clamped to the shoulder of the specimen, for obtaining AE signals. Silicone grease was used as an acoustic coupling medium. AE signals from the transducer were processed by a PAC-SPALTAN 3000 acoustic emission system. The system gain was set at 60 dB, and 40 dB was used as a signal threshold.

Fig. 1. Tensile specimen with an AE sensor set for environmental testing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile strength in air and acid environment

The ultimate fracture strength was affected by the environment under which the test was carried out. The shorter immersion time (up to 48hrs.) and the pre-damaged levels had no effect on the tensile strength. This is clearly shown in Fig.2. Under acidic condition, the strength was 30% lower than in air. This reduction of strength was due to fiber corrosion.

The tensile strength of pre-stressed specimen in air was the same as that of unstressed specimen, irrespective of damage levels and acid immersion time if under 48hrs. Also, the specimens with zero and 30% pre-stress levels did not decrease in the tensile strength after long time immersion (720hrs.). By the report of Caddock[3] on diffusion of HCl in unsaturated polyester resin, it has been clarified that acid penetration doesn't occur under zero load. This phenomenon can explain our tensile test results with specimens at low pre-stress levels after long time immersion. On the other hand, under the combined conditions of high pre-stress and long immersion time, the tensile strength in air was considerably reduced. This is because of the specimens with high pre-stress levels can allow acid penetration during long time immersion. The negligible effect of acid was thought to be caused by the difficulty of acid transport to the load bearing fibers even at such a short immersion time.

In concluding, during the tensile test under acidic condition, the environment penetrated occurred more easily due to the enlargement of the initial damage. This of course reduced the tensile strength. The phenomenon responsible for the difference between the tensile strength tests in air and acid environment was whether the acid penetration occurred or not.

3.2 SEM observation

As can be seen in Fig.3, the SEM observation showed fiber pulling out on the fractured surface of specimen fractured in air (a). This may indicate that, failure such as debonding occurred in the fiber-resin interface before fiber breakage. Under acidic environment (b), broken fibers can be seen on the same plane in an outer area within the load bearing fiber bundles, in contrast to the results obtained in air. This indicates that a preliminary fiber breakage occurred before debonding of interface, as a result of acid attacking under the stress level less than those which could develop debonding on the interfaces [2].

Fig. 2 Tensile strength in air and acid environments, in relation to pre-stress load and immersion time.

Fig. 3 SEM Photograph of fractured surface of GFRP broken in air (a) and acid environment (b).

In Fig.4, the fracture surface of the tensile test in air was shown on the specimens with pre-stress levels of 0,30,40,50% after acid immersion for 720hrs. The fracture surface with fiber pulling out could be seen in the specimens with pre-stress levels up to 30%, while a specific smooth surface caused by acid corrosion may be seen at 40 and 50% levels.

From Fig.4, the number of broken but non-pulling out fibers in a bundle, consisting of about 800 filaments, was plotted against the pre-stress level, as shown in Fig.5. In the case of tensile test under acidic environment, fracture took place with a fixed number of fiber breakages (90-140 filaments; or 1/9-1/6 of total number in the bundle) without pulling out. In the tensile test in air, fiber breakage occurred with pulling out in the specimens with pre-stress up to 30%, but in the specimens beyond 40% level the behaviour was almost the same as that under acidic environment.

Fig. 5 Pre-stress level vs. number of broken fibers without pulling-out in a bundle.

Fig. 4 SEM Photograph of fractured surface of GFRP broken in air after acid immersion of pre-damaged specimen.

3.3 Kaiser effect and influence of acid

AE activity strongly reflects the levels of pre-damage, even in the case of keeping the strength, i.e. AE measurement can microscopically detect the initial level of damage in fracture of GFRP.

In Figs.6 (1), and (2), AE-tensile stress-time curves, for test in air using pre-stressed specimen with 30% and 50% load, are shown. The load up to the dotted line was given as a preliminary stress without AE activity. This means that the Kaiser effect is defined for no propagation of damage under such a pre-stressed level. Under acidic condition, in contrast, the pre-stressed specimen with 50% load, showed AE activity at a lower stress level than that attained by the preliminary load application as clearly shown in Fig.6 (3). The reason may be due to the enlargement of the pre-stressed damage, through which the acid can be easily percolated by the capillary action and can break the load bearing fibers with AE generation.

3.4 Effect of pre-damage

Figure 7 shows the cross-sections of specimens which were pre-stressed by using the tensile testing machine. The pre-stress levels are 30, 40, and 50% of the original strength. At the stress level of 40%, the formation of cracks occurred perpendicular to the load direction, permitting rapid transport of acid. At 30% stress, this crack formation not detected.

Fig. 6 Results of tensile test in air or acid environments, showing effect of stress and time on AE activity.

Fig. 7 Micrograph of cross-section from pre-damaged specimens.

Figure 8 shows the tensile test results of acid-immersed non-stressed specimens in air. The immersion time (0, 1 and 48 hrs) had no effect on AE activity. This implies that acid penetration in GFRP would be restricted within such a short immersion time.

The results of the tensile test in air on the 50% pre-stressed specimen after acid-immersion, are shown in Fig.9. AE signals were clearly recognized at the early stage (e.g. 1 hr) of acid immersion. This was followed by increasing AE activity with the immersion time. Although the AE generation was thought to be originated from resin cracking, the debonding of fiber/resin interface, and fiber fracture, the AE signals seen in the figure would mainly be originated from fiber breaking which easily took place at a relatively low stress level. This consideration may be supported by the result of SEM observation on the fracture surface which showed the increase in number of the broken fibers without pulling out with increasing acid-immersion time; that is, the longer the immersion time, the easier occurred the fiber breaking.

Fig. 8 Results of tensile test in air, showing relation between Immersion time and AE activity. (without pre-stressing)

Fig. 9 Results of tensile test in acid, showing relation between Immersion time and AE activity. (pre-stress condition; 50% of tensile strength)

3.5 Effect of matrix resin

If the existing cracks is thought to be directly concerned with the environmental stress corrosion, the resistance must be increased by using a tougher and more anticracking resin. In Fig.10, the relationship is shown between the stress level and the accumulative AE hit numbers on the 60-100dB level, for the AE activity of Resins A and B in the tensile test.

The AE activity level of Resin B in the accumulative hit numbers at 70% stress is almost the same as that of Resin A at 50% stress. This would result in allowing both resins to generate a similar level of stress cracking. But in the specimens with the same level of pre-stress, say 50% stress, there could be seen the difference in the property, between both resins, such as the retention of tensile strengths in air after acid immersion, shown in Fig.11. The result indicates an important effect of resin toughness on the environmental stress cracking under acidic conditions.

Fig. 10 AE cumulative hits on tensile tests of GFRP with two type matrices.

Fig.11 Effect of matrix property on retention of tensile strength with immersion time.

4 CONCLUSION

- 1) In the tensile test under acidic conditions, load-bearing glass fibers of FRP can rapidly be corroded to weaken their strength by acid, which easily penetrates through cracks in a matrix resin generated during the test.
- 2) The existence of cracks is necessary for acid transport. The combination of cracks and acid accelerates degradation in GFRP, leading to a remarkable decrease in strength.
- 3) In the early stage of deterioration, there exists a precursor phenomenon which can be detected by the examination of AE activity, prior to beginning of decreasing strength.
- 4) The resistance to crack generation largely depends on the toughness of matrix resins: the higher the toughness, the more resistant is the crack generation.

References

- 1) Hogg, P.J. and Hull, D., Metal Science, 14,441 (1980)
- 2) P.J.Hogg; Composites Science and Technology, 38,23 (1990)
- 3) B.D.Caddock, K.E.Evans and D.Hull; J.Materials Sci., 22,3368 (1987)
- 4) G.P.Marshall and D.Harrison ; Plastics and Rubber Processing and Application, 2,269 (1982)
- 5) R.Hill, A.Cowking and W.S.Carswell; Composites, 20,(3)215 (1989)
- 6) M.Kumosa, D,Hull and N.Price; J.Materials Sci., 22,331(1987)